

Speculation on Meaning of Shannon's Entropy and Stochasticity of Measurement Versus System

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Shannon's entropy is usually considered to measure the stochasticity in a system in a certain manner. If, however, one applies it to a deterministic classical bound problem, as in (1), then there is no stochasticity in the system. Rather, it seems one must introduce stochasticity into the measurement. Basically, one has an x axis which may be resolved into equal dx units and may then map this into dt values which differ as $C/|v(x)|$, where $v(x)$ is velocity. In other words, one has a relative value of $dt(x)$ to dx or a distribution which may be normalized to 1 and then called a probability even though there is no stochasticity in the system. We have pointed this out in previous notes and have also noted that one may introduce stochasticity into the measurement. For example, given that one has L , the length between classical turning points, one may pick any x value with equal probability and send in a photon to see if a hit occurs. The probability of a hit seems to be proportional to dt/T , where T is the period. In such a manner, one may have many bound systems and send a photon at random x points into each as a set of N trial runs. One may calculate the probability for the N runs and take \ln to find Shannon's entropy. This single value, to the power of e seems to give an average hit probability for the entire bound system, but the stochasticity is entirely in the measurement process. Different bound systems yield different entropies, i.e. different generic average hit probability values. This then seems to be the role of this measurement entropy, although it does characterize the bound system in a certain manner which may be ascertained experimentally.

In the case of a quantum bound state, it seems that $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, is linked both to the time spent classically in dx and a quantum resolution stochastic time. Thus, there is stochasticity in both the measurement and system if one calculates Shannon's entropy as $-\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*(x)W(x)\}$. In other words, this Shannon's entropy seems to be some kind of combined measure of stochasticity. We ask: What should one do to capture only the stochasticity of the quantum bound system? Quantum mechanics seems to create resolution regions and so $W^*(x)W(x)$ has various crest regions. We suggest that each crest region has a base related to the amount of classical time spent in this length. One may renormalize each crest in $W^*(x)W(x)$ so that its area is proportional to the classical time spent in the region. One may then take this new $W1^*(x)W1(x)$ and use it to calculate a Shannon's entropy which is hopefully a better measure of the stochasticity of the quantum bound system and not of the measurement approach.

Classical Bound State Entropy and Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by:

$$S = -k \sum_i f(x) \ln(f(x)) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } f(x) \text{ is the probability for } x.$$

It seems, however, that given a function $y=f(x)$ over a length L , one may normalize its area to 1 and then call it a probability function even though there is no stochasticity present.

This is done in the case of a classical bound problem for which each equal dx is mapped to a dt given by $C/|v|$ where v is velocity (1). Then:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)| \quad ((2))$$

This yields a Shannon's entropy, suggesting stochasticity, but there is none in the system. We suggest, as we have in a previous note, that one must consider the stochasticity to be in the measurement process. In particular, one may choose an x in the length L (between the classical turning points) with equal probability in N identical sets of the bound system. One may then send in a photon to see if it collides with the particle. The photon is sent in along the y axis while the particle moves along the x . The probability to collide should be given by:

$$dt/T = Cdx/(T|v|) \quad ((3))$$

In such a way, one may consider the probability for the outcome of N trial runs where N is very large. Ignoring the equal probability for each x choice one has:

$$P(N \text{ runs}) \text{ proportional to } Cx/(T|v(x)|)^N \quad ((4))$$

Taking \ln of both sides yields a probability of the form:

$$\exp(-N \text{ Shannon's entropy}) \text{ with } k=1 \quad ((5))$$

Thus, all of the stochasticity is in the measurement and one really finds: $\exp(-\text{Shannon's entropy})$ as a kind of average generic probability for a photon hit for a given bound system regardless of the x point chosen. One may then choose different bound systems, i.e. different potentials $V(x)$ or total energy and obtain a different entropy linked to a different average generic probability for a photon hit on the particle.

Physically, however, it is not clear why one is interested in an average probability for collision, although in a sense it does describe the bound system, albeit from a stochasticity of measurement point of view.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum free particle has a genuine stochasticity because it is described by $\exp(ipx)$ and there is probability in both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ to be at different x values even though on average one moves with a constant speed.

A quantum bound problem is solved using:

$$-1/2m \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + V(x)W = E_n W \quad ((6))$$

$W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ contains crests and troughs and $W^*(x)W(x)$ a series of crests of different heights and base widths. We suggest that the intrinsic stochasticity of $\exp(ipx)$ is

present because of the resolution crests, but also the measurement stochasticity of the classical bound problem. We thus suggest that:

$$-\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*W\} \quad ((7))$$

combines both of these stochasticities and does not measure the stochasticity of the quantum system. It would be good to have a measure of the quantum stochasticity alone.

To achieve this, we suggest that one must consider each crest in $W^*(x)W(x)$ because these are the quantum resolution lengths. One may calculate a time for each crest base using classical mechanics because one knows $v(t)$ and $x(t)$ for the classical problem. Then:

$$\int dt \text{ over a crest base} = \int dx/|v(x)| \text{ over the crest base}$$

$$\text{where } .5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((8))$$

One may then calculate the area of each crest $W^*(x)W(x)$ and normalize it to represent the classical times given by ((8)). In other words, one multiplies $W^*(x)W(x)$ for a crest region by:

$$\text{Classical time in base/ Area of crest} \quad * W^*(x)W(x) \text{ on a crest by crest basis} \quad ((9))$$

This leads to a new $W1^*(x)W1(x)$. This new density may then be used in a Shannon's entropy calculation. In this way, the probability of each crest region corresponds to the average classical time spent there and hopefully one has a measure of quantum stochasticity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that given any distribution of two variables (smooth function) over a length L , one may normalize the area and call this a probability distribution even though there is no stochasticity. This is done for the classical bound problem (1) and a Shannon's entropy computed. We suggest that this entropy corresponds only to measurement entropy. In other words, entropy is used in $\exp(-\text{entropy})$ to yield an average probability for a photon to hit the classical particle at any x point. The photon is sent in along the y axis choosing x points with uniform probability. One may then use entropies for different bound states to characterize each, but the stochasticity seems to remain in the measurement.

We argue that a quantum bound state has both this measurement stochasticity as well as the inherent quantum stochasticity already found in $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that $W(x)$ has crests and troughs and $W^*(x)W(x)$, a series of crests with different heights and base lengths. Given that resolution is key in quantum mechanics, we suggest calculating the area of each crest and renormalizing it to correspond to the classical time spent by the particle traversing the base length. This leads to a different $W1^*(x)W1(x)$ which may then be used in a Shannon's entropy calculation and will hopefully lead to an entropy measure which captures the stochasticity of the quantum system and not the measurement.

References

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